

A Study of Ethnographical and Topographical Aetiology of Acute Encephalitis Syndrome (AES) in Bihar

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Abstract: In this paper a non-epidemiological etiology of the encephalitis endemic was studied in the Muzaffarpur and Gaya districts of Bihar. There may be some common reasons of such endemics at both locations that may be related to ethnicity and parental traits coupled with high temperature variations and individual and social traits. It was found that most children were dark skinned and suffering from acute poverty. There was no proper availability of drinking water and sanitation. In addition, in some cases parental ignorance and stunting may be also responsible for high incidences. Children required special care during peak of the summer. It would be costly to check such menace by vaccination because of many strains of the virus. The menace having high mortality of almost 20-30 percent that may be controlled or prevented by changing in parental traits especially related to child care.

Key words: *Acute Encephalitis Syndrome (AES); Child Morbidity and Mortality in Bihar, Ethnographic and Topographic Etiology*

Objectives: The purpose of this research was to explore the inconclusiveness involved with the encephalitis related morbidity and mortality in different areas of Bihar. The research mainly focused two districts of Bihar Muzaffarpur, Gaya because the large number of mortifies, and mortality reported from there. This preliminary work demanded a dedicated study involving all the available information to open new sources. Therefore, this particular research only studied the comparative ethnicity, topographies of the affected areas, parental traits, vector density, and control measures. The study of the aetiology was not medical, clinical, or fully epidemiological. The work was most probably the first to test the explanatory possibilities of the diversified causes of the large-scale child morbidity, mortality, and disablement in Bihar due to *Acute Encephalitis Syndrome (AES)*. The study would contribute new sources and additional approaches to the fields of Public Health, Social & Community Medicine, and Study of Tropical Diseases.

Introduction

The infection with JEV ranges from non specific febrile illness to a severe meningoencephalomyelitis illness. The risk of Japanese encephalitis varies by local ecology and season. In temperate areas of Asia, human disease usually peaks in the summer and falls down after that and these seasonal epidemics can be explosive with thousands of cases occurring over a period of several months; whereas, in the subtropics and tropics, transmission can occur throughout the year, with the disease at a peak during rainy season. Still, there was no any concrete evidence about the disease. It has been widely conceived that outbreaks of an unexplained acute neurologic illness has been affecting young children and associated with a high case-fatality rates have been reported in the Muzaffarpur district of Bihar state in India since 1995. The outbreaks generally peak in June and decline weeks later with the onset of monsoon rains. There have been multiple epidemiologic and laboratory investigations of this syndrome, leading to a wide spectrum of proposed causes of the illness, including infectious encephalitis and exposure to pesticides. An association between illness and litchi fruit has been postulated because Muzaffarpur is a litchi fruit-producing region. To better characterize clinical and epidemiologic features of the illness that might suggest its cause and how it can be prevented, the Indian National Centre for Disease Control (NCDC) and CDC investigated outbreaks in 2013 and 2014.. Although a specific

etiology has not yet been determined, the 2014 investigation has identified the illness as a hypoglycemic encephalopathy and confirmed the importance of ongoing laboratory evaluation of environmental toxins to identify a potential causative agent, including markers for methylene cyclopropyle glycine (MCPG), a compound found in litchi seeds known to cause hypoglycemia in animal studies (1-3). Current public health recommendations are focused on reducing mortality by urging affected families to seek prompt medical care, and ensuring rapid assessment and correction of hypoglycemia in ill children (Akash Srivastava, 2015).

The problem:

Encephalitis is inflammation of the brain caused either by an infection or through the immune system attacking the brain as post-infectious or autoimmune Encephalitis (Society, 2015). Not all encephalitis were infectious and however, could cause damage to children and even adolescents and adults. It could cause damage to the brain, memory, body functions, epilepsy, and deaths. The disease appeared as mystery because of uncertain diagnosis, and despite improvements in specific and supportive treatments, *Encephalitis* had a high mortality rate as high as 30 percent in certain cases (Dowell, 2014). The acute phase of the illness could last anything from a few days to several weeks. In some cases, the person may be in a coma for a much longer period. The acute stage may be followed by a phase of rapid improvement that slows down, but recovery can continue over the years to come. No two cases of *Encephalitis* will have an identical outcome (Easton, 2015). Three out of twenty of infected children have the probability of dying and 20 to 40 percent would have the probability to be left with permanent aftereffects. Vaccination could be the only cure as the survey also said that one in a million children who had vaccination would develop *Encephalitis* from the vaccination that is less than the incidence of all types of Encephalitis (Crowcroft, 2006).

At all India level in total numbers of *Encephalitis* cases reported year wise were 5,167 in 2010, 8,249 in 2011, 8,344 in 2012, 7,825 in 2013 and 9,912 cases in 2014 up to 17 December were reported among them numbers of mortality were recorded as 679 in 2010, 1,169 in 2011, 1,256 in 2012, 1,273 in 2013 and 1,495 up to 17 December 2014. In Bihar up to October 2014, 928 cases and 314 deaths due to *Acute Encephalitis Syndrome (AES)* were reported (India, 2015).

Encephalitis could easily term as an endemic in several parts of Bihar, an eastern province of India. However, a lack of unanimity found about the disease not accurately diagnosed and patients mostly treated following symptoms. In the absence of any conclusive diagnosis those common symptoms referred as *Acute Encephalitis Syndrome (AES)*. Different versions found about the etiology of the disease, however, mostly believed that it spreads because of the vectors. Nevertheless, newly introduced *West Nile Encephalitis (WNE)* spread through contaminated water. The outbreak of diseases usually coincides with the onset of climate change where the density of vectors fluctuates for transmission of the infectious organism either biologically or mechanically, while encephalitis due to other viruses specially entero-viruses occurs throughout the year as it is a waterborne disease (M. Saminathan, 2013).

Encephalitis considered as a vaccine preventable disease, however, due to multiplicity of viruses there could not be any common vaccine and cost of vaccination for the entire range of encephalitis would prove utter expensive. So far, vaccination against the *Japanese Encephalitis (JE)* administered in the affected areas, however, its prevalence rate of *Japanese Encephalitis (JE)* still not very certain among all encephalitis cases. According to a study, *Japanese Encephalitis (JE)* cases among the *Acute Encephalitis Syndrome (AES)* cases constituted only 2 percent of the cases, affecting 0-4 year age group (Ragini Mishra, 2014). Contrary to that, according to another study, the trend of *Japanese Encephalitis (JE)* suggested that the problem might escalate and larger epidemics would occur in the future; suggesting serious steps for combating the *Japanese Encephalitis (JE)*, including the development of more efficient surveillance methods and differential diagnosis (Shailendra K. Saxena, 2009).

There is tremendous data gap in India in the relationship between ethnicity and health (K. K. Sharma, 2013). Despite intermingling of different ethnic groups, still several distinctions existed largely. Several diseases have a certain degree of prevalence among different ethnic groups. India could be ethnically divided in four major zones such as North & West, East, Northeast, and South. Bihar falls in the eastern zone and different ethnic groups existed despite intermingling. In Bihar, ethnicity largely preserved in the caste system. Caste maintained its several characteristics such as ethnicity, endogamy, and hierarchy. Caste system existed among Muslims also despite conversions centuries ago. The pattern of encephalitis in India certainly shows a great degree of prevalence in eastern and southern parts (MOHFW, 2015).

In several social groups, the reason for high child morbidity and mortality could be due to parental neglect and deliberate stunting (S. Faruqi, 2013). In social groups, not well educated and with low-income, high birth and death rates of children found common. Therefore, study of parental traits becomes important and no any such dedicated study reported in the affected areas. Parental traits becomes so important for prevention, especially in an endemic area.

Likewise, study of topography turned extremely significant for several diseases (Chatterjee, 2013). Topographical studies with the help of QGIS and remote sensing made significant progress in studying etiology of a disease. Topographical changes over the last few decades has been tremendous. It might have contributed due to climate changes and lead to symptoms such as erratic, delayed, or early monsoon, abnormal cold, and summer. Riverbeds filled with silts, and drainage water accumulating at a particular location resulted in large-scale

contamination of ground water, so far considered safe for human consumption. The large population in Bihar sustained due to agriculture and plenty of water. The fertile land usually provided 2-3 crops annually. However, irrational use of insecticides and pesticides adversely affected the food chain. It also could induce increases in the density of vectors as they reemerged stronger (Bose, 2013).

Literature review

There were several research articles indicated Lychee (*Litchi sinensis*), a locally grown sweetener fruit as a possible cause (Singh, 2014) (Bhattacharya, 2014). In some other parts of the world such as Bangladesh, Vietnam symptoms of encephalitis found in litchi growing areas. An association of AES with lychee is important, interesting, and challenging. Investigators in Vietnam believed that some unknown virus caused the disease, while in Bangladesh the disease was not thought to be infectious but was attributed to pesticides used in the orchards. Curiously, both these studies and the one from Muzaffarpur showed positive correlation between the number of cases and amount of lychee harvest (Sahni, 2013) (Paireu, 2012) (Islam, 2013) (Biswas, 2012).

In a study at Muzaffarpur, the investigators noted colonies of fruit-eating bats and the tendency of children eating fruits fallen to the ground and suggested the possibility of a bat virus (through saliva) contamination of fruits) as a cause of the disease (Samuel, 2013).

In a study by Gopal Shankar Sahni, Department of Pediatrics, S. K. Medical College, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India termed heatstroke as a medical emergency with serious complications and requires prompt treatment. It is associated with multi-organ dysfunction with high mortality and substantial neurological sequelae (Sahni, 2013).

In their study Srinivasa Rao Mutheneni, Suryanarayana Murty Upadhyayula, and Arunachalam Natarajan found that Japanese Encephalitis (JE) transmission in temperate areas is dependent on climatic factors; however, this study suggested that the effects of weather variables such as rainfall, temperature, and relative humidity might be responsible for increase of vector populations and the JEV infection. Apart from these, the other factors like agricultural practices, virus-amplifying hosts such as pigs and its density and virus reservoirs might also play a major role in the disease transmission in the study areas (Srinivasa Rao Mutheneni, 2014).

In their study D. S. Dinesh, K. Pandey, V.N.R. Das, R.K.Topno, S.Kesari, V. Kumar, A. Ranjan, P. K. Sinha, and P. Das has found that children belonging to poor families in pediatric age suffered the most. They also caused local topography, heat stroke, and litchi fruit as possible factors (D. S. Dinesh, 2013).

There were many other studies I have reviewed that mostly relates to outbreak investigations and surveillance studies. Almost three fourth studies were related to morbidities among children. In periodical order, I found two studies published before 1975. Thirty-seven articles I found belonging to the period 1975 to 1999. The rest of the article published after year 2000, therefore it could say that increase in the study, and publication on encephalitis has picked up over the year 2000. The first Acute Encephalitis Syndrome, an AES outbreak investigation was from eastern India in 1973 and subsequently several outbreak investigations reported between 1975 and 1999. Most studies reported epidemics during summer or

raining (between May and October), and mostly from northern and eastern parts of India.

A study also found that the immune system of ill-nourished children; in hot and tropical weather, conditions quickly deteriorated (P. K. Srivastava, 2012).

The first epidemic outbreak of Acute Encephalitis Syndrome appeared in North Bihar districts during 2011 particularly among poorest community in the pediatric age group. Patient Data were collected from Shri Krishna Medical College and Hospital, Muzaffarpur and Krishnadevi Deviprasad Kejariwal Maternity under KDK Matri Sadan Trust in Muzaffarpur. The topography of the affected villages was studied using a standard questionnaire. The disease appeared in pediatric age group (median 5 years between 3 months to 10 years) coinciding with the litchi (*Litchi chinensis*) fruit season. A total of 85 cases appeared in Muzaffarpur and a few in two districts namely Sitamarhi, Sheohar and East Champaran with 31% death from June-July, 2011. The symptomatic treatments were given to the patients due to lack of diagnosis. Heat stroke was suspected as major possible factor (D. S. Dinesh, 2013).

Even it was suggested that the disease in question is not acute viral encephalitis, but a form of acute encephalopathy probably mediated by a toxin related closely to the litchi cultivation in the region. Much of the evidence linking MCPG to these outbreaks has been largely circumstantial due to the lack of properly conducted epidemiological studies, histopathological demonstration of toxic effects of the toxin, and inability to perform analysis of any specific metabolites in the body fluids of the ill children. The experts involved in the investigations should urgently look into these aspects before claiming success in conclusively diagnosing the illness (Das, 2016).

Recurrent unexplained outbreaks of acute encephalitis in children, coinciding with the litchi harvesting season have been reported from India (West Bengal and Bihar), Vietnam and Bangladesh. The clinical, biological, and immunologic characteristics of the patients suggest a viral etiology, the causative agent could not be ascertained in each of the outbreaks. As a result, several hypotheses have been put forward namely heat stroke, pesticides or hypoglycin A as the cause of the AES syndrome. The investigators of this study, report for the first time that the evidence gathered so far points towards a viral etiology. The causative virus has remained unidentified and further studies using high throughput sequencing technology and sequencing micro-arrays are required for identification and characterization of the incriminating virus. Also the hyperglycemia induced by litchi fruit may have aggravated the encephalitis rather than actually causing (Bhaswati Bandyopadhyay, 2014).

A detailed study has been done on the geographic distribution of JEV and incidence and burden of disease in India. Vaccination proves to be the best measure to protect the individual against any disease. So, large scale immunization of susceptible human population is highly important to prevent this deadly infection. In India, vaccinations against Japanese encephalitis are administered in areas where the disease is hyper endemic (Aditi Singh, 2012).

It appeared from all those literature reviews that five blind men are trying to describe an elephant. There was a total lack of unanimity among the professionals and medical experts over the issue. The literature review could be summed as that there is no much literature found about any major studies on ethnic pattern, topography, and parental traits in the project area.

Research questions:

“How the ethnicity, topography, climatic conditions, parental traits, and lack of preventive measures could be responsible for the child morbidities and mortalities due to Acute Encephalitis Syndrome (AES) in Bihar”.

Research hypothesis:

The research is based upon the hypothesis that the biological etiology of the disease most probably may have been complimented due to ethnicity, topography, climate, and lack of preventive aspects including suitable behaviors, vaccination and control of vectors.

Methodology

I visited all those encephalitis areas to study the ethnicity, topography, climate, traits, and socioeconomic conditions of the patients. I obtained detailed case history of the patients from the patient registry system of *Kejriwal hospital, S.K Medical College, Muzaffarpur, A.M College, Gaya* for the last five years. A list of suffering household was then prepared and I visited 321 households (201 in Muzaffarpur and 120 in Gaya district) for the required information. The socioeconomic status, sources of drinking water and food chain was investigated. The ethnicity, temperature variations, topography, vector density, individual traits, relevant agrarian-agricultural issues investigated as per academic customs. The cropping patten was also investigated. The topography of those areas was studied using satellite pictures. Sources of rivers originated from neighboring Nepal were also studied.

However, first of all I also draw a detailed picture of the actual conditions based on the main sources such as hospital records mainly case history, government, and non-government statistics, community archives, newspapers, and other specialized publications, epidemiological studies, and field interviews.

The key sources and informants for this study was situated in Patna such as Public Health Administration, Institutions such as Research Centers of Indian Council of Medical Research, Tropical Research Institutes that used to capture several epidemiological data and clinical reports. The project remained based primarily in Patna however; numerous field visits conducted in the affected areas.

Findings

The cases of encephalitis were reported from wide areas and since Muzaffarpur and Gaya being the core place where any specialized medical treatment facilities were available. Therefore, in general, it gave the impression that cases were localized to Muzaffarpur and Gaya districts, however, it was found that cases were all adjoining areas.

The study of households revealed that most of the victims belonged to very poor economic backgrounds and mostly they and their parents were dark skinned. Even stunting apparently could be a major reason, especially in those households where the body complexions of the respective mothers and fathers mutually differed. In such cases, if the mother was fair complexioned then father was dark skinned or even vice versa. Stunting may be also very much as case even if both parents were having same body complexions. However, in those households where both mother and father were having a similar body complexion the case of stunting was low. In cases where mother and father were having different body complexions or colors of skin despite they lived happily,

nevertheless both parents exhibited a degree of cruelty towards children and never gave proper attention to child care.

This study could be concluded by terming the endemic of encephalitis in Muzaffarpur and Gaya were due to different reasons. However, it was common in both places that cases were mostly reported during the peak of summer. Both places have distinct topography as Gaya is a hilly terrain and relatively hotter than Muzaffarpur. Common to both places was the pathetic drainage and sanitation systems. The rivers around Muzaffarpur became so fealty with solid wastes and it needed to improve the solid waste disposal at both places. Enecepalitis is also reported from Gorakhpur situated at a distance of about 200 kilometers from Muzaffarpur. The core finding the temperature variation and continued high temperature as one of the reasons. In addition, in the absence of any medical and biochemical evidences it could be said that since more and more children used to consume litchi it may be reason. In fact, most cases were reported during the peak of summer and to avoid heat there has been traits among children and their parents to feed them on litchi. However, acute heat may be the most valid reasons because encephalitis reported from the Gaya district also where litchi is not produced however, may be transported from Muzaffarpur. The two places were situated at a distance of over 155 kilometers. Encephalitis mostly affected dark skinned children and poor. Therefore, there could certainly be some ethnic reasons. However, it could not be the sole reason because high temperatures also affected several other of the state. The issues related to ethnicity certainly an interesting aspect to explore further because all most all cases belonged a particular ethnic group living mainly in poverty, and dependent on paddy agriculture. The river beds in an around Muzaffarpur could be the reason. Definitely, temperature variations and sudden and sustained increase in temperature above 40 degrees Celsius have caused the disease. Most of the cases reported sustained high temperature during which children suffered from the so called disease, however, no one sure about the disease that remained mystical and treated largely on the symptoms.

The current AES/JE surveillance system has been strengthened in Bihar following numerous cases and both the state and central government are very active in those areas, however they are more facing the medical angle and ignoring the social, and trait theories. The effect of interventions undertaken for AES control would never be adequate ignoring those social and traits related issues. Gaps and challenges in the control of AES outbreak constitute key lessons that need to be incorporated as strategic planning. Laboratory facilities have been strengthened. Even micro- planning before the AES transmission season needs to be strictly implemented. As the disease outbreak is aggravated by multi-factorial factors, intersectoral coordination with various departments may also prove to be effective in the control of the disease outbreak (Ragini Mishra, 2014).

Conclusion:

Poverty, ethnicity, lack of sanitation and water coupled with high temperature may be reasons behind large mortality and morbidity due to encephalitis. In addition, parental traits, ignorance, and deliberately stunting may be a specific reason. Recently, some scientists have associated it with a consumption of litchi. However, it would be mostly advisable to prevent children from in taking large amount of litchi especially empty stomach. It also needed to find the reason of encephalitis in Gorakhpur and aid to the current study.

However, certainly ethnicity and parental traits, and poverty may be a suitable reason.

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